

THE EXPERIENCE IN SURGICAL TREATMENT OF CONGENITAL HYDRONEPHROSIS IN CHILDREN

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Abstract. *It is important to suggest that congenital anomalies in the development of different organs and systems are registered with a frequency of 50-60 per 1000 newborns. At the same time, the share of congenital hydronephrosis (CH) accounts for more than 50% of all "obstructive uropathies" and is 1:800 newborns, while the disease is characterized by an asymptomatic course, and the leading place in the cause of its occurrence is occupied by stenosis of the pyeloureteral segment [4, 7, 8, 9, 10]. At the same time, many questions and problems associated with a long stay of the patient in the hospital, long-term recovery, led to the search for the gentlest methods of surgical treatment of this pathology [3, 7, 11]. This will allow rational use of existing methods, taking into account the modern possibilities of minimally invasive surgery than the use of traumatic lobotomy approaches. In this regard, despite the constant interest in the problem of congenital hydronephrosis, questions about clear criteria for surgical treatment are still debatable [1, 2, 6].*

Keywords: *asymptomatic course, pyeloureteral segment, traumatic lobotomy approaches.*

Purpose of the study. To improve the results of surgical treatment and optimize the tactics of managing children with hydronephrosis based on the use of a modified method of urethropoanastomosis.

Materials and methods. The study included the analysis of the results of treatment of 691 children with congenital hydronephrosis aged 3 to 15 years based on the urology departments of three medical institutions in Fergana Valley, which were conditionally divided into two groups:

- comparison group - 337 (48.8%) children (from 2013 to 2017), where surgical tactics (treatment and diagnostic program, choice of surgical interventions, preoperative preparation and postoperative management) are based on generally accepted principles

- the main group - 354 (51.2%) children (from 2018-2022), where the treatment is based on improved tactical treatment and diagnostic algorithms and the developed urethropoanastomosis.

What is more important, in case of congenital hydronephrosis in children, 143 (20.7%) were diagnosed under the age of 3 years, 236 (34.2%) - at the age of 4-7 years and 312 (45.1%) - at the age of 8-15 years, with a predominance of boys - 504 (72.9%), compared to girls - 187 (27.1%) (Fig. 1).

Definitely, the maximum number of children were admitted to the urology departments with stage III HG, which amounted to 75.3% of the total number of hospitalized patients.

At the same time, stage III hydronephrosis was most frequently detected in 247 (73.3%) children in the comparison group and 273 (77.2%) in the main group, significantly less often - stage II (13.9% - 9.8%) and - stage IV (12.2% - 12.7%), respectively (Fig. 1).

In most patients, the cause of VH were internal factors, such as stenosis of the ureteral junction, which accounted for 242 (71.2%) and 265 (74.8%), respectively, high origin of the ureter in 11 (3.2%) and 7 (1.9%), embryonic adhesions in 37 (10.9%) and 36 (10.1%) children. Among

the causes of an external nature, operated on in the period from 2013 to 2017 (comparison group), an aberrant vessel was detected in 37 (10.9%) patients, congenital ureteral kink in 10 (2.9%) children, in the period from 2018 to 2022 (main group) in 42 (11.8%) and in 4 (1.2%) patients.

Figure 1. Distribution of patients by age and gender

Figure 2. Distribution depending on the causes of CH.

For determining the severity of PUS obstruction, we used the classification proposed in 2007 by the Society of Fetal Urology [12] modified by Onen A. (Fig. 2).

Figure 3. Localization of congenital hydronephrosis.

Figure 3. Degrees of hydronephrosis in groups of sick children. Certainly, in children with hydronephrosis, left-sided lesions were predominant – 205 (60.8%) and 218 (61.6%), right-sided localization was noted in 27% and 28.5% of cases, bilateral – in 11.2% and 9.8% of cases. (Fig. 3).

It should be noted that, despite the early appearance of signs of hydronephrosis, the diagnosis was detailed and clarified in 20.7% of cases later than 3-5-7 years of the disease, after repeated manifestations of pyelonephritis. Since in some cases hydronephrosis is detected as an accidental finding (16.8%), during an ultrasound examination of the abdominal cavity and retroperitoneal space.

The preoperative examination of children included:

1. Assessment of the patient's general somatic status;
2. Instrumental research methods to clarify the level and cause of obstruction of the ureteropelvic segment;
3. Choice of treatment method.

In order to reduce radiation exposure, if hydronephrotic transformation was suspected, computed tomography was performed against the background of the excretory phase of intravenous urography.

In the comparison group, the classical lateral lumbotomy with a wide incision according to Federov up to 10 cm prevailed – in 316 (93.7%) children, especially in young children (18.3%), which subsequently led to the occurrence of postoperative hernias, to cicatricial deformations of the skin of the younger generation of children (Fig. 4).

Figure 4. Approaches applied in the comparison group

Laparoscopic approaches were used in the initial period of implementation of minimally invasive techniques, which was used only in 14 (4.1%) children, with conversion to traditional access in 6 (42.8% of 14) of them. There were attempts to perform laparoscopic retroperitoneal approaches in children aged 1-3 years (1.2%). Laparoscopic transperitoneal access was used in 8 (2.4%) children.

It should be noted that conservative measures were performed in 5 (1.5%) children with I and II degrees of hydronephrosis and in 2 (0.6%) children with IV degree of hydronephrosis with concomitant diseases (chronic renal failure). It was decided to conduct dynamic observation in these patients (Fig. 4).

Besides that, Andersen-Hines pyeloureterostomy was performed in 92 (27.2%), resection of the ureteral ureterostomy with end-to-end pyeloureterostomy in 58 (17.2%), laparoscopic dissection of embryonic cords in 14 (4.1%), Foley operation in 119 (35.3%), nephrectomy on one side was performed in 6 (1.7%) children with stage IV hydronephrosis, and transection of the aberrant vessel in 37 (10.9%) children. In the comparison group, after all operations, drainage of the renal pelvis was performed for approximately 10-15 days.

Figure 4. Types of operations in the comparison group by age groups

The average duration of open pyeloplasty using the traditional approach in the lumbar region (according to Fedorov) was 91 ± 12 min. ($p < 0.05$). The average duration of surgery using the laparoscopic approach was 120 ± 11 min. ($p < 0.05$).

In the main group of patients, while choosing the method of pyeloplasty using the open method, we adhered to the following principle: minimal trauma - maximum effect.

In the main group, open pyeloplasty was performed using an improved posterolateral lobotomy mini-approach with an incision of no more than 5 cm - in 71 (20.1%) children, especially in young children (9.8%) (Fig. 5).

Additionally, experience with laparoscopic surgeries has shown that minimally invasive surgeries require the use of incisions that, while not being so traumatic, would create a wide and convenient access for the surgeon to all sections of the pulmonary cerebral artery.

Based on the shortcomings and omissions in the comparison group and the accumulation of experience in the use of minimally invasive methods of kidney surgery (laparoscopy), this led to an increase in the number of laparoscopic approaches - in 281 (79.3%) children, with conversion to a modified posterolateral mini-approach in only 1 (0.3% of 281) of them.

It should be noted that in 1 (0.28%) child with grade I hydronephrosis and in 1 (0.8%) child with grade IV hydronephrosis, conservative measures were performed due to the parents' refusal

of surgery due to the severity of the child's condition. It was decided to conduct dynamic observation in these patients.

Figure 5. Approaches applied in the main group.

The average duration of open pyeloplasty using a modified mini-access in the posterolateral surface of the lumbar region (according to the clinic method) was 61 ± 7 min, 30 ± 5 min shorter than in the comparison group (91 ± 12 min). ($p < 0.05$). The average duration of surgery using a laparoscopic access was 70 ± 8 min, i.e. 50 ± 3 min shorter than in the comparison group (120 ± 11 min) ($p < 0.05$). In the main group, Andersen-Hines pyeloureterostomy was performed in 27 (7.6%) cases, resection of the ureteral junction with the application of a modified end-to-side pyeloureterostomy in 283 (79.9%) cases, intersection of the aberrant vessel in 9 (2.5%) cases after preliminary testing of the renal blood supply by the vessel by clamping it, resection of the ureteral junction with the application of a modified end-to-side pyeloureterostomy with displacement of the aberrant vessel in 23 (6.5%) cases, and nephrectomy on one side was performed in 1 (0.28%) child with stage IV hydronephrosis (Fig. 6).

What is more important, the resection of the ureteral junction with the formation of pyeloureterostomosis must comply with the following rules: eliminate the causes of obstruction, the newly formed ureteral junction must be of sufficient area, devoid of a section of dysplastic cells, and the formed section must function well and improve the general condition of patients, relieve them of various ailments, i.e. adhere to the principle: elimination of the obstruction focus, normalization of function and evacuation function.

It should also be noted that conservative measures were performed in 2 (0.5%) children with grade I hydronephrosis. In these patients, resolution of the patency of the ULJ was noted in dynamics with a return to the initial parameters within an acceptable time frame and normal functionality in one child, and in one child, an operation with an excellent outcome was subsequently performed with a transition to changes in the ULJ with impaired patency.

Figure 6. Types of operations in the comparison group by age groups

Results and discussion. Comparison of immediate treatment results according to the following parameters:

1. Duration of intervention and anesthesia.
2. Amount of blood loss.
3. Severity of pain syndrome.
4. Drainage time.
5. Frequency of intra- and postoperative complications.
6. Need for analgesics per bed-day.
7. Postoperative bed-day.

Surprisingly, immediate results of treatment with urethroploanoastomosis using a modified method:

Moreover, duration of manipulation (minutes) with an open method using a mini-access - 61 ± 7.2 min (in the comparison group - 91 ± 12 min), duration of the operation using a laparoscopic access - 70 ± 8.1 min (in the comparison group - 120 ± 11 min)

Duration of anesthesia (minutes) with an open method using a mini-access 68.3 ± 1.5 , using a laparoscopic access 80 ± 3.1 min.

Blood loss (milliliters) 30.1 ± 1.5 ml

Duration of bed rest (days) with an open method using a mini-access - 1.8 ± 1.2 days, using a laparoscopic access - 1 ± 0.3 days.

Duration of wound drainage (days) - 2.6 ± 0.1 days.

Complications of the i/o period in the main group - 5 (1.4%), in the comparison group - 41 (12.4%).

The need for injection of narcotic analgesics after classical open surgery for 3.9 ± 0.6 bed-days, in the main group after a modified posterolateral mini-access they were necessary for 1.3 ± 0.6 bed-days, after laparoscopic uretheropyeloanastomosis - 1.0 ± 0.2 bed-days.

The postoperative bed-day was significantly shorter and amounted to 6 ± 0.42 days compared to patients who underwent classical traditional open lobotomy - 20.8 ± 3.2 .

It is known to everyone, in the comparison group, iatrogenic injuries were found in 41 (12.4%) patients. With the traditional open method of surgery, the most common complications were bleeding from the retroperitoneum (3.9%) and wounds (2.7%) with a wide incision. Kidney damage was noted in 3 (0.9%), damage to the renal vessels during their isolation and mobilization in 7 (2.1%) children. In the initial period of mastering the laparoscopic technique of operations in the comparison group, intraoperative complications were noted in 9 (2.7%) children, with conversion to traditional access in 6 (1.8%) - (42.8% of 14). Of these, intestinal wall damage in 1 (0.3%), omentum damage in 1 (0.3%), damage from the renal vessels in 2 (0.6%) children, bleeding from the retroperitoneum was noted in 1 (0.3%) child during an attempt to perform retroperitoneal laparoscopy. In the main group, with open surgery from a mini-access, iatrogenic injuries were observed only in 2 (0.5%) cases in the form of bleeding from the wound and retroperitoneum, in 1 (0.28%) case from the wound, while the length of the incision did not exceed 6 cm. Bleeding was mainly stopped by conservative measures. With laparoscopic urethropoloanastomosis, complications were observed only in the form of bleeding from the trocar wound - 3 (0.8), with conversion of access to a "mini-access" in 1 (0.2%) case.

Comparative analysis showed that in the main group, in relation to the comparison group, the frequency of iatrogenic injuries decreased by 11% (from 12.4 to 1.4%), with a decrease in the number of conversions by 1.6% (from 1.8 to 0.2%).

In the comparison group, postoperative complications associated with surgical intervention were noted in 31 (9.4%) children, with a total of relumbotomy - in 3 (0.9%), relaparoscopy - in 2 (0.6%) children.

Of these, external urinary leakage was noted in 5 (1.5%), anastomotic failure in 4 (1.2%), hematuria in 3 (0.9%), drainage dysfunction in 5 (1.5%), frequent and painful urination in 7 (2.1%) children. In the main group, postoperative complications associated with surgical intervention were noted in 3 (0.8%) and in none of the cases relaparotomies were performed. In the postoperative period, the cosmetic effect of the postoperative wound is also noteworthy. The average size of the incisions after open operations in the comparison group was 10.4 cm (± 2.6), the minimum incision size was 80 mm, the maximum 100 mm. In the main group, the average wound size after open operations with a mini-access was 40.2 mm (± 2.8), the minimum incision size was 40 mm, the maximum 50 mm.

It is not a secret to anyone that comparative analysis showed that in the main group, in relation to the comparison group, the frequency of postoperative complications associated with surgical intervention decreased by 8.6% (from 9.4 to 0.8%), with a decrease in the number of relumbotomies by 0.9% (from 0.9% to 0%) and relaparoscopies by 0.6% (from 0.6 to 0%). General complications in the comparison group as a whole were diagnosed in 20 (5.9%) patients with a fatal outcome in 5 (1.5%) cases, while in the main group - in 2 (0.5%) patients with a fatal outcome in 1 (0.2%) case (a decrease in general complications by 5.1% and mortality by 1.3%).

Conclusions. Thus, by optimizing the tactics of managing patients with congenital hydronephrosis, we achieved an increase in the proportion of patients with no complications in the postoperative periods by 25.6%, and a decrease in the number of repeated surgeries from 0.9% to 0%. The developed improved urethropoloanastomosis creates optimal conditions for the healing of the newly created anastomosis and made it possible to reduce the frequency of general and specific complications from 5.9% to 0.5%, eliminate the need for repeated traditional interventions and the likelihood of long-term recovery of renal function ($P=0.005$).

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